

What is Business Consulting?

[James Liggett CPA](#) explains that Business consultancy is a problem diagnosis and data analysis service for the company, which aims to help entrepreneurs improve their management.

With it, it is possible to reduce costs, make processes more efficient, optimize finances, plan business expansions and improve the work of the human resources sector, among other approaches.

According to James Liggett CPA, this type of help, coming from a specialist, serves to solve different obstacles related to the business.

It may be, for example, that business management is inefficient, sales are down, or that the business owner needs to create a strategic plan for their projects.

Thus, business consultancy involves an exchange of experiences and knowledge between a specialist and a company.

The [highly experienced professional](#), James Liggett CPA, shares that the consultant is a qualified professional with market knowledge and experience.

He then works with business managers to help them solve problems - or even identify them.

The consultancy's role, therefore, is to collect information about the company, develop a strategic action plan to put it into practice and, finally, analyze results.

According to [the certified public accountant](#), James Liggett CPA, it is during this exchange of knowledge that the consultant is able to bring insights and proposals to the company's leadership, who may or may not accept the suggestions.

The main objective is to verify challenges and opportunities for growth in the company and assist in decision making.